

A Study of Psychosocial Factors Associated with Relapse in Alcohol Dependent Patients

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Abstract:

Introduction: Alcohol dependence is a major chronic relapsing disorder. Relapse is a phenomenon which is multifactorial. It is mostly due to the combination of various factors such as patient characteristics, environmental and the drug reinforcers. Risk Factors for relapse are intrapersonal factors and interpersonal factor. Intrapersonal factors reside within the person. It has various subdivisions like coping with anger or frustrations, coping with emotional states which are harmful, coping with physical states due to previous use of substance, coping with other physical states which are harmful, testing personal control, to enhance positive emotional state, cue mediated temptation and giving in to temptation even in the absence of cues. Interpersonal factors are interpersonal conflicts that resulted in anger or frustration, direct and indirect social pressures and to enhance positive emotional states in a situation related interpersonally like celebrations.

Aim: To assess the association between the coping strategies and self-efficacy with relapse in alcohol dependent patients.

Materials and Methods: Sample Size: 120 subjects.

Type of study: Prospective study.

Study tools: Alcohol abstinence self-efficacy scale, Coping Behaviours Inventory.

Results: The subjects with good coping behaviour have more chance to remain abstinent, and the subjects with poor coping behaviour have more chance for relapse. Positive coping strategies to the situations that lead to relapse help the individual to remain abstinent for more periods.

Keywords: Alcohol, Self-Efficacy, Coping behavior, Alcohol dependence.

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Introduction

Alcohol use is widely prevalent in India. Alcohol dependence is a chronic and progressive disorder featured by a loss of control over the use of alcohol with subsequent social, legal, psychological & physical consequences. Alcohol consumption has risen dramatically during the last four decades and was accompanied by an increase in the social, psychological and physical problems. [1]

Alcohol use widespread in India in rural and urban areas with prevalence rates generally varying from 23% to 74% in males and it is not that common in females but in certain sections and communities, alcohol use is found to be prevalent at the rate of 24% to 48 % in females. In 2005 surveys in India showed 62.5 million people using alcohol. Of them 17.4% (10.6 million) had an alcohol use disorder and among hospital admissions, 20-30% are due to alcohol-related problems. [2] Alcohol dependence is characterized by craving, compulsion, the

primacy of drinking over other activities and a state of neuronal adaptation leading to physical and mental disturbances on withdrawal. [3] Alcohol dependence is a major chronic relapsing disorder. Relapse is a phenomenon which is multifactorial. It is mostly due to the combination of various factors such as patient characteristics, environmental and the drug reinforcers. [4]

Risk Factors for relapse are intrapersonal factors and interpersonal factor. Intrapersonal factors reside within the person. It has various subdivisions like coping with anger or frustrations, coping with emotional states which are harmful, coping with physical states due to previous use of substance, coping with other physical states which are harmful, testing personal control, to enhance positive emotional state, cue mediated temptation and giving in to temptation even in the absence of cues. Interpersonal Factors are interpersonal

conflicts that resulted in anger or frustration, direct and indirect social pressures and to enhance positive emotional states in a situation related interpersonally like celebrations.

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Materials and Methods: Sample Size: 120 subjects.

Study Design: Prospective study.

Sampling Method: Convenience sampling

Study Group: The study includes patients who attend the psychiatry hospital with relapse after treatment. A sample of 120 patients fulfilling the inclusion criteria is studied.

Inclusion criteria:

- Patients who are between 18 and 70 years of age
- Patients who fulfil ICD-10 criteria for research for alcohol dependence and received treatment.
- Patients who were previously diagnosed as alcohol dependence and received treatment and again attend OP for treatment with relapse.
- Patients who have consented to the study.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients with comorbid psychiatric disorders, major physical illnesses, organic brain syndrome.
- Patients with multiple substance abuse except for nicotine use.

Operational Procedure:

- The study includes patients who attend the psychiatry hospital with relapse after treatment. A sample of 120 patients fulfilling the inclusion criteria is studied.
- Coping behaviours and self-efficacy will be assessed using coping behavioral inventory, Alcohol abstinence self-efficacy scales respectively.
- The above sample is followed for a period of 6 months and assessed for the number of patients who presented with relapse and those who are completely abstinent.

Ethical Issues: Informed consent was obtained from each patient. All were explained regarding the nature and rationale of the study.

Study Tools:

Self-designed semi-structured data questionnaires were used which includes the following:

- (a) Socio-demographic data sheet.
- (b) Clinical profile sheet.

Alcohol Abstinence Self Efficacy Scale: This is a 40 item scale. Among them 20 questions were on temptation and given a score from 0 to 4. Remaining 20 questions were on confidence levels and given scoring from 0 to 4.

Those 40 questions were categorised into 4 subheadings based on the factors that lead to relapse. They were 1) Negative Affect 2) Social Factors 3) Physical and Other Concerns 4) Craving and Urges.

Coping Behavioural Inventory: It is 36 item self-administered inventories. The inventory includes a list of 14 cognitive and 22 behavioral options. The respondent indicates how often he/she uses each coping behaviour to avoid relapse. Frequency of use is rated on a four-point scale from 0 to 3.

Statistical Analysis: Statistical analysis of the data was carried out using SPSS software version 23. To assess the association between the coping strategies and self-efficacy with relapse in alcohol dependent patients relevant statistics were applied.

Results

A total of 120 subjects diagnosed as alcohol dependence with relapse after 1 month of abstinence were included in the study. Of them 102 were followed up for 6 months.

The mean age of the total sample is 37.91 years (SD: 10.25). Majority of the subjects belonged to rural area (61.76%), and the remaining to urban area (38.24%). 24.51% of the sample were illiterate, 23.53% studied up to primary school, 20.58% up to secondary school, 15.69% studied up to intermediate, 15.69% were graduates. 69.61% of the sample were married, while 30.39% were unmarried. 20.59% of the sample belonged to upper middle class, 28.43% of the sample belonged to upper lower class, 39.22% of the sample belonged to lower middle class, 11.76% of the sample belonged to lower class. 62.75% of the sample comes from nuclear family, remaining 37.25% of the sample comes from joint family.

The mean age of initiation of alcohol is 20.96 years, and the mean duration of intake of alcohol is 16.37 years with SD of 8.80, mean duration to develop dependence is 11.61 years with SD of 6.14 years, the mean duration alcohol dependence is 4.88 years. The results showed the age of initiation of 82.35% of the sample is <24 years and 16.67% of the sample between 24-34 years and only 0.98% initiated alcohol between 34-44 years.

The duration of intake of alcohol of 23.53% of the sample is <10 years, 39.22% of the sample is between 10-20 years, 28.43% of the sample is between 20-30 years, 7.84% of the sample is between 30-40 years and 0.98% of the sample is between 50-60 years. Out of the total sample

n=102, 52.94% of the sample has family history of alcohol dependence. Remaining 47.06 % has no family history of alcohol dependence.

The time to develop dependence of 42.16% of the sample is <10 years, 48.04% of the sample is 10-20 years, 7.84% of the sample is 20-30 years, 1.96% of the sample is 30-40 years. The duration of dependence of 56.86% of the sample is <5 years, 31.37% of the sample is 5-10 years, 9.81% of the sample is 10-15 years, 1.96% of the sample is 15-20 years.

The mean age of initiation of alcohol in relapsed group is 20.74 years and in abstinent group is 21.69 years. The mean duration of intake of alcohol in relapsed group is 16.87 years and abstinent group is 14.65 years. The mean time to develop dependence in relapsed patients is 11.89 years and abstinent group is 10.60 years. The mean duration of dependence in relapsed group is 5.08 years and abstinent group is 4.17 years.

Table 1: Comparison of clinical variables among relapsed group and abstinent group

	Relapsed group(n=79)	Abstinent group(23)	Mean difference
Age of initiation of alcohol	20.74	21.69	-0.95
Duration of intake of alcohol	16.87	14.65	2.22
Time to develop dependence	11.89	10.60	1.29
Duration of dependence	5.08	4.17	0.91

Table 2: The SES score of relapsed group and abstinent group at initial assessment and after follow up

	Relapsed group (n=79)	Abstinent group (n=23)	Mean difference
SES score at initial assessment	95.17	92.39	2.78
SES score at follow up	92.98	84	8.98

Table 3: The mean differences of temptation scores of SES components at initial assessment

	Relapsed group (n=79)	Abstinent group(n=23)	Mean difference
Negative affect	13.83	11.69	2.14
Social factors	12.93	11.65	1.28
Physical factors	13.18	11.30	1.88
Craving and urges	11.96	11.13	0.83

Table 4: The mean differences of temptation scores of SES components after follow up

	Relapsed group (n=79)	Abstinent group(n=23)	Mean difference
Negative affect	12.02	3.26	8.76
Social factors	11.88	2.95	8.16
Physical factors	11.03	3.13	7.9
Craving and urges	10.83	3.13	7.7

Table 5: The mean differences of confidence scores of SES components at initial assessment

	Relapsed group (n=79)	Abstinent group(n=23)	Mean difference
Negative affect	9.63	11.73	-2.1
Social factors	11.69	12.65	-0.96
Physical factors	10.10	10.52	-0.42
Craving and urges	11.44	11.69	-0.25

Table 6: The mean differences of confidence scores of SES components after follow up

	Relapsed group (n=79)	Abstinent group(n=23)	Mean difference
Negative affect	12.59	17.69	-5.1
Social factors	11.53	17.78	-0.96
Physical factors	11.74	17.78	-6.04
Craving and urges	12.48	18.26	-5.78

The CBI score of abstinent group is low compared to relapsed group at initial assessment . After 6 month follow up period the CBI scores of abstinent group is significantly decreased compared to relapsed group .

Table 7: The mean CBI scores of the relapsed group and the abstinent group at initial assessment and after follow up

	Relapsed group (n=79)	Abstinent group (n=23)	Mean difference
CBI score at initial Assessment	81.53	75.82	5.71
CBI score at follow up	73.11	32.30	40.81

Discussion

This study is one of the few studies, which explores the extent of association of various psychosocial factors with relapse in patients of alcohol dependence. Among the psychosocial variables, coping behaviour of the patient to adverse situations had the highest association with relapse, followed by high-risk situations. In this study, 53% had a family history of alcohol dependence, and 47% had no history of alcohol dependence. This finding is comparable with both Suresh Kumar et al [5]. And Purushottam et al.[6] studies that more than half of the sample had a family history of alcohol dependence. This study concludes that children brought up in families with parents having alcohol dependence are more prone to initiate alcohol. This study also concludes that patients with a family history of alcohol dependence had more chance for relapse and less chance to remain abstinent even after treatment. The SES confidence scores of negative affect, physical factors, and craving and urges showed statistical significance between the relapsed group and abstinent group on t-test. These results replicate with Suresh Kumar et al [7]. Study there is the statistical significance of SES scores among relapsed and abstinent group. This study is comparable with Kamal Prakash et al. study that relapsed group had high SES scores and high temptation scores compared to abstinent group stating that patients with high temptation score have more chance of relapse. However, the abstinent group had high confidence scores compared to relapse group confirming that patients having high confidence levels to remain abstinent in a given situation has more chance to remain abstinent when compared with relapse group. The CBI scores of the abstinent group is low compared to relapsed group. On CBI low score indicates good coping behaviour and a high score indicates poor coping behaviour.

Conclusion

Subjects with family history of alcohol dependence are more prone to initiate alcohol at earlier age and they have more chances of relapse after treatment. In the abstinent group, relatively the age of

initiation of alcohol is greater, and the chance of going into alcohol dependence is at a later age, the chance of relapses is comparatively less and the period of abstinence is also more. Subjects with poor self-efficacy have more chance for relapse. The subjects with good coping behaviour have more chance to remain abstinent, and the subjects with poor coping behaviour have more chance for relapse. Positive coping strategies to the situations that lead to relapse help the individual to remain abstinent for more periods.

Limitations: The study has a smaller sample size. This study is done in hospital setting, so the results cannot be generalised to community.

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7. Indian Journal of Basic and Applied Medical Research; June 2017: Vol.-6, Issue- 3, P. 375-384 Evaluation Of Various Psychosocial And Clinical Factors Associated With Relapse In Patients With Alcohol Dependence At A Tertiary Care Hospital: An Observational Study 1Dr. Kamal Parkash*, 2Dr. Ravi C Sharma, 3Dr. Dinesh Dutt Sharma.